

ONLINE X-RAY FLUORESCENCE SCREENING OF ORE FOR SILVER AT THE MINES OPERATED BY KAZAKHMYS CORPORATION LLC

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ABSTRACT. This paper discusses the process and methodological aspects of X-ray fluorescence online monitoring of ore silver grade at the underground mines and open pits operated by Kazakhmys Corporation LLC. The analysis was complicated by the requirement to: a) ensure reliable silver grade determination of the ore, starting at 1+ ppm; b) sample mine faces in vertical sections to a height of up to 7 m. For geophysical online monitoring of the ore material in the walls of mine workings and in the broken rock mass, a portable energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer RPP-12T (Aspap Geo LLC, Alma-Ata) was developed, assembled, and comprehensively tested. The results of investigations carried out using the RPP-12T spectrometer are discussed. The data collected during the investigations made it possible to implement online ore silver grade monitoring in the underground mines and open pits operated by Kazakhmys Corporation LLC.

Key words: X-ray fluorescence method, energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer RPP-12T, online ore grade monitoring

Introduction

Kazakhmys Corporation LLC is a major copper company operating in Kazakhstan. Ore is mined at the Zhezkazgan, Balkhash, and Karaganda sites. Cuprous sandstone deposits Zhezkazgan, Zhaman-Aybat, Zhilanda Group (Itauz, Eastern Saryoba, Western Saryoba, Kipshakpay, Karashoshak), as well as complex copper-containing polymetallic deposits characterised by a wide grade range of valuable, associated, and impurity minerals are currently operated: the porphyry gold-copper Nurkazgan deposit, the pyrite-copper-lead-zinc Kuzmuryu and Akbastau deposits, the gold-pyrite-copper-lead-zinc Abyz deposit, the Sayak group of copper-skarn deposits, the porphyry copper Konyrat deposit, and the porphyry copper-uranium Shatyrol deposit (Satpayeva, 2005).

To efficiently conduct exploration and mining operations at such complex deposits, reliable means are required of online geophysical monitoring of the elemental composition and metal grade of the ore in in-situ rock, broken bulk rock mass, transportation vehicles, on process conveyor belts, and in exploration core samples.

In mining geophysical sampling, the emphasis is now placed not only on monitoring the grade of the primary (copper) mineral, but also on monitoring the grade of associated minerals (first of all, silver). Extraction of associated silver is a significant factor contributing to the economic performance of Kazakhmys Corporation LLC. Managing controlled extraction of associated silver and other associated ore minerals at the mining operations of Kazakhmys Corporation LLC is an urgent operational challenge. This study addresses this problem.

Factors complicating the implementation of effective online monitoring of ore silver grade are the following:

- Low silver grade ranging from 15 ppm in the ores of the Zhezkazgan, Zhaman-Aibat, and Zhilanda cuprous sandstone deposits to 2–3 ppm at the Konyrat and Nurkazgan deposits;

- Horizontal and gently sloping ore bodies at the Zhezkazgan, Zhaman-Aibat and Zhilanda deposits requiring sampling of mine faces and ledges in vertical sections up to 7 m high, which causes problems when delivering the instrument sensors to the required height and ensuring safety during geophysical sampling;

- Control system for associated silver mining will be effective only if the geophysical monitoring technology is able to reliably measure ore silver grades starting at 1+ ppm, which is the limit for the majority of online analysers, both laboratory and portable.

It is clear that ensuring reliable determination of ore silver grade by geophysical methods in the process of geophysical online monitoring of ores is a very complex task, both methodologically and technically. In addition, given the scale of production at Kazakhmys Corporation LLC operations, the technology vendor and its service centres must be located in Kazakhstan.

The study presented here addresses the above-mentioned problems.

Materials and methods

Since 1971, energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence (EDXRF) has been the primary method of geophysical ore sampling and analysis at Zhezkazgan. This method was chosen as the main research method.

In our geophysical investigations, we used portable EDXRF spectrometers RPP-12T, developed by Aspap Geo LLC (Almaty, Kazakhstan) specifically for measuring low grades of silver, cadmium, and a number of other elements, as well as for X-ray fluorescence sampling (XRF) of high faces (Dosmukhamedov, Lezin, 2011; Dosmukhamedov et al., 2012; Dosmukhamedov et al., 2013). A simplified mathematical model for calculating the abundances of elements in the EDXRF spectrometer RPP-12T is discussed in detail in (Yefimenko 2009).

The portable EDXRF spectrometers Spectroscan-GEO (SPECTRON, Ltd, St. Petersburg, Russia) and Elvax GEO (Elvatech, Ltd, Kyiv, Ukraine) were considered as an alternative (Moschevikin, Soloviev, 2020). But they did not fit in terms of weight parameters, the lack of the ability to raise the sensor to a height of 7 m and the considerable remoteness of firms from the mines of Kazakhmys Corporation LLC. For the same reasons, the use of EDXRF spectrometers of well-known world brands was not considered.

Two modifications of the RPP-12T EDXRF spectrometer were used in the studies: underground mine version (Figure 1A,

2B), open-pit version (Figure 2A, 2B) and core version (Figure 1B). RPP-12T has a powder sample XRF function (Figure 3) for XRF of powder samples on the surface or XRF sampling of cuttings from holes drilled into the roof and bottom of mine workings directly in the underground mine.

The standard handheld spectrometer RPP-12T comes with two-meter rods (in this case, face XRF sampling height will be 4 m (Figure 2C.1). For Zhezkazgan, the number of rods was increased to 4–5 (Figure 2C.2). Sensor weight is 1.5 kg.

Fig. 1. EDXRF spectrometer RPP-12T

Fig. 2. XRF sampling using RPP-12T

Fig. 3. Powder sample XRF function

Our know-how represents use of a mass-produced smartphone (Figure 1C and 2B) with an Android operating system and an impact-resistant body (protection class IP67) as the registration and processing unit. Competing solutions use pocket personal computers, whose capabilities are much lower.

Wireless (via Bluetooth) data transmission from the sensor to the processing unit significantly increases the safety of the sampling process in high mine faces. RPP-12T supports mine face XRF sampling for 34 elements: Cu, Zn, Pb, Ag, Cd, As, Se, Ba, Fe, Mo, Mn, Ti, V, Cr, Co, K, Ca, Ni, Ga, Br, Rb, Sr, Zr, Y,

In, Pd, Nb, Sn, Sb, Te, Bi, W, Th, U. The field of view of the XRF sampling surface is 4–5 cm²; measurement exposure at one observation point is from 5 sec; detection limits for most ore elements range between $n \cdot 10^{-4} \%$ and $n \cdot 10^{-3} \%$.

Solutions that make it possible to measure silver grade starting at 1+ ppm by using RPP-12T are as follows:

- high-speed silicon drift detector (SDD);
- small-sized X-ray emitter 50 kV, 10 W;
- optimised excitation of the analytical profiles of silver K-series;
- state-of-the-art high-performance electronics;
- reliable methodology and capable software.

The above device features made it possible to increase the luminosity (input load over 100 kHz) of the excitation and detection unit and the signal/background ratio and, thereby, significantly improve the sensitivity of the RPP-12T spectrometric channel to silver, which made it possible to confidently operate the spectrometer at silver grades from 1+ ppm with an XRF exposure at the observation point of 10 sec.

RPP-12T has a highly durable and protected design and does not require high operator's skills. The continuous operation time of RPP-12T on same battery set (in the 1st rod) is at least 10 hours.

To demonstrate the ability of the RPP-12T spectrometer to measure silver grades starting at 1+ ppm, an extensive testing and experimental programme was carried out (Yefimenko et al., 2014, Yefimenko et al., 2016). The main testing conditions are the following:

1. Core samples from exploration boreholes at the Zhezkazgan deposit were examined in Core Sample mode as follows: a) XRF measurements on 1 m core samples in boxes in a continuous mode with the sensor moving along the core sample at a rate of 20 sec/m, Figure 4B; b) XRF of 1 m core

samples with a sampling increment of 10 cm (10 sampling points per m) and 20 cm (5 sampling points per m) with an exposure of 10 seconds and 5 seconds for each increment; c) verification XRF of 1 m core samples using the measurement modes specified in (a) and (b). Verification XRF in (b) had a slight shift.

2. XRF of the coarsely ground ore sample from a railway car (5–6 kg each) taken from two ore compositions (Kresto-7 open pit) at Zhezkazgan Concentrator 1. On each sample, 35–40 measurements were made with an exposure of 10 seconds (Figure 4A). Measurement mode was Naturally Occurring Ore.

3. XRF of reference ore specimens (of State Standard Ore Samples - SSOS) (Tsentsgeolanalit, 2021) in Naturally Occurring Ore mode. Five measurements of 10 seconds each were taken across the sample in Naturally Occurring Ore mode.

4. XRF of exploration core sample by comparing the analysis results obtained with RPP-12T and an alternative portable EDXRF spectrometer Spectroscan Geo by NPO Spektron LLC (St. Petersburg, Russia). It should be emphasised that the XRF conditions were different: RPP-12T was used for core XRF in a continuous mode (Figure 4B); Spectroscan Geo was used for core XRF using a tripod (Figure 4C). We note that Spectroscan Geo is heavier (2.4 kg), has only two 1 meter long thin rods, and comes with a less powerful pocket personal computer (624 MHz vs. 2500 MHz).

5. High face XRF - at a height of 7 m.

6. XRF of powder ore sample using the Sample Analysis function. The measurement mode was Powder Sample. The measurement exposure time was 30 seconds.

7. XRF of Standard ore reference samples (SSOS –3029) - the measurement mode was Powder Sample and the measurement exposure 30 seconds. Sample Analysis option was used.

A. Car sample

B. RPP-12T core sample

C. Spectroscan Geo core sample

Fig. 4. Experimental work

Results and discussion

The results from studies of ore samples from exploration boreholes at the Zhezkazgan deposit are presented in Table 1.

The data in Table 1 shows that the fit between the average silver grades in 1 m core sample intervals determined by XRF and chemical assay is fully compliant with the standards required by the mine geologists at Kazakhmys Corporation LLC operations (Yefimenko et al., 2016). The results of a study on off-grade copper intersections (not shown in Table 1) showed

that RPP-12T is capable of reliable online monitoring of silver grade, starting at 1+ ppm.

The XRF results from measurements of the coarsely ground ore sample from a railway car taken from two ore compositions (Kresto-7 open pit) at Zhezkazgan Concentrator 1 were as follows: copper 3.03% and 2.28% (chemical assay 2.98% and 2.39%), silver 57.5 ppm and 37.7 ppm (chemical assay 52.5 ppm and 39.4 ppm), cadmium 4.1 ppm and 6.3 ppm (chemical assay 4.4 ppm and 5.9 ppm). The results confirm the good fit between the XRF data obtained by using RPP-12T and the chemical assays.

Table 2 shows an XRF report for the reference ore sample No 51 (Tsentsgeolanalit, 2021) with a low silver grade (verified grades are Cu = 0.15%, Zn = 0.48%, Pb = 0%, Ag = 2.2 ppm, Cd = 37.0 ppm). As it can be seen, the RPP-12T is capable of reliably determining silver grades of 2.0 ppm.

The results from exploration of core sample by comparing the analysis results obtained with RPP-12T and the alternative portable EDXRF spectrometer Spectroscan Geo are presented in Table 3. Data on chemical assays are also shown in the

Table. As it can be seen from Table 3, the RPP-12T spectrometer performed very well giving data nearer to the chemical analyses figures.

Concerning the high face analysis, it was shown that the RPP-12T spectrometer is capable of carrying out XRF of mine faces to a height of 7 m. Figure 2C illustrates XRF at a height of 3 m and 6 m.

Table 1. RPP-12T Core sample XRF for silver, ppm

Int. No	Chemical assay	Core sampling mode									
		Continuous		10 points/m				5 points/m			
				10 s		5 s		10 s		5 s	
		Primary	Control	Primary	Control	Primary	Control	Primary	Control	Primary	Control
41	3.7	4.2	4.2	3.2	3.7	2.6	3.5	3.0	3.3	3.3	1.9
42	4.7	5.4	4.3	3.5	4.2	4.2	3.6	2.9	3.0	3.3	5.1
40	5.2	5.5	4.9	5.6	4.5	3.8	5.1	3.7	7.5	2.3	5.2
61	8.5	9.2	8.2	7.8	7.0	6.6	7.0	5.6	10.1	7.0	5.7
47	15.4	16.2	15.5	13.9	16.4	12.6	13.5	10.6	17.1	14.0	11.2
55	16.1	17.4	15.8	16.5	17.1	18.0	15.9	20.7	12.3	15.4	20.6
56	20.2	17.7	23.4	15.7	19.0	23.0	21.4	20.1	11.3	28.3	17.7
48	37.0	45.3	43.1	40.4	45.0	41.6	38.9	39.2	43.9	38.4	42.4
50	46.1	44.1	44.5	44.6	45.4	41.3	43.5	43.6	45.6	40.2	42.4
52	17.2	17.1	17.9	16.6	16.0	17.3	18.1	18.3	17.4	16.2	17.9
Avg.	17.41	18.2	18.2	16.8	17.3	17.1	17.1	16.8	17.2	16.9	17.0
σ		4.6	4.4	3.6	2.4	1.9	2.1	3.6	1.4	3.2	2.3

Table 2. XRF of the reference ore sample No 51 (Tsentsgeolanalit, 2021)

Point grade						
No	Cu, %	Ag, ppm	Zn, %	Pb, %	Cd, ppm	Fe, %
1	0.13	2.3	0.51	0.00	38.7	1.50
2	0.14	2.3	0.49	0.00	38.1	1.52
3	0.15	1.6	0.49	0.00	38.2	1.59
4	0.14	2.4	0.48	0.00	38.2	1.52
5	0.14	2.1	0.50	0.00	35.0	1.47
Average	0.141	2.0	0.493	0.00	37.6	1.52

Table 3. Simultaneous core studies using the EDXRF spectrometers RPP-12T and Spectroscan Geo

No	Interval, m		Grade								
	from	to	Cu, %			Zn, %			Ag, ppm		
			Chemical assay	RPP	GEO	Chemical assay	RPP	GEO	Chemical assay	RPP	GEO
1	131.3	132.4	0.93	0.848	0.830	0.003	0.0033	<0.01	50.7	44.7	46.7
2	135.4	136.4	0.50	0.443	0.450	0.004	0.0033	<0.01	20.8	17.4	21.3
3	136.4	137.5	0.46	0.432	0.470	0.004	0.0036	<0.01	21.3	18.0	23.2
4	137.5	138.5	0.43	0.419	0.430	0.004	0.0038	<0.01	16.8	14.7	19.4
5	138.5	139.5	0.34	0.316	0.340	0.005	0.0038	<0.01	17.8	19.5	17.3
6	139.5	140.5	0.22	0.231	0.270	0.005	0.0041	<0.01	6.1	6.1	8.0
7	140.5	141.5	0.42	0.418	0.560	0.005	0.0042	<0.01	22.6	24.8	27.2
8	141.5	142.5	0.37	0.579	0.400	0.005	0.0064	<0.01	20.7	23.7	21.2
9	142.5	143.5	0.44	0.449	0.450	0.004	0.0037	<0.01	24.6	24.1	25.5
10	143.5	144.5	0.20	0.204	0.230	0.004	0.0034	<0.01	6.8	5.9	7.3
Average			0.431	0.434	0.443	0.004	0.0040	<0.01	20.82	19.89	21.70

The results from analyses of powder ore samples are presented in Table 4. A good fit between the average copper

and silver grades found with the aid of XRF and chemical assay was shown.

Table 5 shows the results of the studies of standard ore reference samples (Tsentgeolanalit, 2021) carried out by RPP-12T and chemical analysis. As it can be seen a good fit is obtained between the average silver and other mineral grades obtained by XRF and chemical analysis. The RPP-12T spectrometer on powder samples of ores ensures the accuracy

of analysis for Ag, Cd, Cu, Zn, and Pb, which falls within the tolerances of "Norms of permissible discrepancies between the results of analyses of products of the copper industry and the lead-zinc industry for the content of basic elements" (ST RK 3126-2017).

Table 4. XRF of powder samples

Element	Method	Sample No									Avg.
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
Cu	Chemical	0.68	0.88	1.43	0.84	3.65	1.33	7.68	7.13	3.95	3,063
%	XRF	0.62	0.91	1.34	0.82	3.61	1.27	8.03	7.17	4.02	3,088
σ , %		8,8	3,4	6,3	2,4	1,1	4,5	4,6	0,6	1,8	0,80
Ag	Chemical	2.4	6.1	10.2	15.1	22.0	32.35	46.7	94.6	174.4	44,88
ppm	XRF	2.9	5.5	8.5	13.1	21.4	32.8	45.6	98.3	176.6	44,97
σ , %		20.8	9.8	16.7	13.2	2.7	1.4	2.4	3.9	1.3	0.20

Table 5. Results from studies on standard ore reference samples (Tsentgeolanalit, 2021) by XRF and chemical analysis

Sample	Analysis	Grade, % (* ppm)				
		Cu	Pb	Zn	Ag*	Cd*
2887	RPP-12T	0.537	0.0356	0.0121	8.6	6.9
	Chemical	0.55	0.037	0.011	9.3	n/a
2888	RPP-12T	1.533	0.1019	0.0243	24.6	7.1
	Chemical	1.55	0.103	0.023	25.9	n/a
2889	RPP-12T	3.149	1.8866	0.786	34.9	70.2
	Chemical	3.16	1.90	0.80	35.0	71.0
2891	RPP-12T	40.312	2.243	2.869	701.5	286.5
	Chemical	40.40	2.25	2.89	707.7	290.0

Conclusion

In conclusions it can be said that the study successfully addressed an extremely challenging from theoretical, methodological, technical point of view, as well as urgent operational problem of implementing geophysical online monitoring of silver grade (starting at 1+ ppm) in the walls of mine faces and mine workings in order to manage planned silver production at the mines operated by Kazakhmys Corporation LLC. The results obtained by using the portable RPP-12T spectrometer and chemical assays show that RPP-12T ensures reliable silver grade determination of the ore (starting at 1+ ppm) while being able to sample mine faces in vertical sections to a height of up to 7 m.

The data collected during the studies made it possible to implement online ore silver grade monitoring in the underground mines and open pits operated by Kazakhmys Corporation LLC.

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